

Report on performance, mass and energy balances and design criteria for gas-diffusion electroprecipitation and electrocrystallization

CHPM2030 Deliverable D3.2

Version: August 2018

CHPM2030

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 654100.

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Published by the CHPM2030 project, 2018

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CHPM2030 DELIVERABLE D3.2

REPORT ON PERFORMANCE, MASS AND ENERGY BALANCES AND DESIGN CRITERIA FOR GAS-DIFFUSION ELECTROPRECIPITATION AND ELECTROCRYSTALLIZATION

Summary:

A literature review has been done on geothermal brines to identify relevant characteristics and compounds of interest (i.e., metals, rare earth elements) that can be potentially recovered using the GDEx technology and are prone to form functional materials with potential commercial interest. On the other hand, as temperature can affect the performance of the system, and since the brine treated by the GDEx technology can be within 20-60°C (as defined by the CHPM proposal), this parameter was evaluated in the system, first using simulated brines. The most important effects of temperature within this range concerned the formation of different products, variations on the system resistance, processing time, level of current, and process efficiency. The long term performance under these conditions was also assessed. Based on the relevant brine compositions obtained from the literature study, experiments with simulated Li-Al brines were conducted, as well as with real brines containing these metals (i.e., Romanian geothermal brines). The formation of mixed metal hydroxides was obtained, which have ample commercial relevance. Finally, the feasibility of employing microbial-electrochemical systems (i.e., bioanodes coupled to GDEx cathodes) was tested, proving that the GDEx system could be operated with lower or negligible power consumption, as well as it could even be used for the co-generation of electricity. Overall, the GDEx process is 2-3 fold more economical than classical mineral processing at the metal concentrations of geothermal brines and its upscalability is feasible.

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1 Executive summary

Gas-diffusion electrocrystallization (GDEx) is an innovative electrochemical technology driven by a rapid one-pot reaction precipitation process, steered at the three-phase junction between a porous gas-diffusion cathode, an aqueous electrolyte and an oxidant gas, wherein the oxidant gas is electrochemically-reduced to its peroxides (e.g., O_2 forms H_2O_2 on its molecular, anionic and radical form). By this process and depending on the operational conditions, the selective removal and recovery of a few metals (e.g., Ce, Fe, Mn, Zn, Cu, La, Pt, Pd, etc.) has been tested at VITO in various matrices, with up to >99 % metal recovery, for most cases, as particles at micro- and nano-scale.

In this study, GDEx was assessed for the recovery of metals from geothermal fluids. **Chapter 3** focuses on a literature review on the composition of relevant geothermal brines (from published peer-reviewed articles), while **Chapter 4** describes the laboratory setup and methodology that was followed during the experiments described in this deliverable. From Chapter 5 onwards, the report focuses on the experiments that were carried out with simulated matrices of geothermal fluids and with real geothermal fluids (i.e., geothermal brines from Romania). In **Chapter 5** and **Chapter 6**, the GDEx technology is reported for the treatment of three different simulated geothermal brines (i.e., meeting characteristics of salinity and relevant metal content from real sites in England, Iceland and Belgium). The long term performance of the process and the effect of the temperature were evaluated in each chapter, respectively. **Chapter 7** is dedicated to the recovery of Li and Al from simulated matrices, under different operational conditions (i.e., chemical composition of the brines, working electrode potential from $-350 \text{ mV}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$ to $-900 \text{ mV}_{\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl}}$, salinity from 5 to 135 g L^{-1} , and temperatures of $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) using a simulated geothermal matrix. Additionally, the presence of Ca ($0\text{-}15 \text{ g L}^{-1}$) and Mg ($0\text{-}1 \text{ g L}^{-1}$) was tested, as their abundance in geothermal brines can form salt deposits on the surface of the electrode—affecting the performance of the system. Finally, **Chapter 8** describes the performance of the GDEx process for the treatment of two real geothermal brines from Romania. Energy and mass balances, and the characterization of the obtained products were analysed from these experiments. Finally, **Chapter 9** introduces the use of microbial electrochemical systems coupled to the cathodic GDEx component, with the aim of lowering the energy consumption of the system.

From the overall results obtained, up to >60 % recovery of total metal content and over 99% recovery of specific individual metals was observed. GDEx is a cost-competitive option to recover metals from geothermal brines, in comparison to classical technologies to recover metals from dilute solutions, as proven by the corresponding Sherwood plots. Furthermore, the formation of different metallic products is observed at different operational conditions, mainly depending on the composition of the brines. These have thus a consequent conditioning on the performance of the system and its energy efficiency. In addition, the formation of mixed metal hydroxides was obtained with the GDEx process. These are highly innovative materials and also hold commercial relevance, demonstrating the potential of GDEx not only for the recovery of these elements from geothermal brines but as a novel synthesis technology.

2 Introduction

2.1. Conventional geothermal processes

Geothermal energy is the energy obtained from the Earth's interior stored in rocks, steam and liquid water in geothermal reservoirs (Edenhofer et al., 2011). Technologies traditionally used to generate electricity from the heat in geothermal brines are (1) condensing flash plants or dry-steam plants, and (2) binary cycle units. In addition, hot brines can be used in cogeneration (CHP) plants, providing thermal energy to surrounding localities. Beyond these traditional applications relying on natural convective hydrothermal resources, enhanced geothermal systems (EGS) have been developed during the last 40 years to extract the thermal energy stored in the rocks supported by hydraulic stimulation (Edenhofer et al., 2011; Lu, 2017).

Geothermal energy is considered a clean and renewable source of energy that is continuously available (Rybach, 2007). Theoretical calculations estimate that the thermal energy reserves in the upper 10 km of the earth's crust account for $\sim 1.3 \times 10^{27}$ J (Lund & Falls, 1960). Using the 2017 global energy consumption rate of approximately 5.6×10^{20} J y^{-1} as a benchmark (British Petroleum, 2017), these energy reserves could secure the global energy supply for 2.3 million years. Due to its advantages, installed capacity of geothermal energy has been increasing over the last years; according to Bertani (2016), it is expected to reach 21,443 MWe by 2020 (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1. Installed world geothermal capacity from 1950 to 2015 (MWe) (adapted from Bertani, 2015).

Improvements on geothermal power systems have mainly focused on exploration to locate new geothermal reservoirs, reducing operational costs and yielding higher energy recovery from the ore bodies—particularly developing and implementing EGS systems. However, relatively little attention has been paid to valorising the brines, whose characteristics make them an advantageous by-product.

The increasing depletion of mineral ores has resulted in greater exploitation costs and the consequent reduction of the economic return of the mining sector—which has translated into rising prices of mineral commodities since the 1960s (Bardi et al., 2016; Meadows et al., 1972; Meadows et al., 2004). As a consequence, it is becoming increasingly difficult to ensure their continuous supply in the coming years. This

crisis is particularly important for critical and rare metals, such as those needed by the electronics industry to, for example, produce the electronic components (i.e., converter, transmitter, etc.) required for manufacturing renewable energy systems. The best approach to address the depletion problem is moving in to a “circular economy” where all the resources (and wastes) can be reused and recycled (Bardi et al., 2016; Bianciardi et al., 1993).

Within the Roadmap to a Resource Efficient Europe published by the European Commission (EC, 2011), the most central policy action proposal to date on resource efficiency has been the circular economy package (EC, 2015). Metals and Critical Raw Materials are a central element for this Circular Economy proposal, as they are continually recyclable; in addition, secondary metals do not face downcycling or quality issues (Hagelüken et al., 2016). Metal recovery and recycling will help to secure Europe’s access to metals, being a key consideration for a competitive economy. In this regard, geothermal brines—currently discarded as waste streams—offer a window of opportunity for the cogeneration of raw metals and other valuable metal-containing materials.

2.2. Geothermal brines

Historically, geothermal brines have been regarded as wastewaters in need of treatment to meet the imposed environmental discharge limits and not as prospective sources for the recovery of marketable metal-containing materials. However, there is a high economic potential on metal extraction from geothermal brines.

The biggest barriers to enable the recovery of metals from geothermal brines are technological, and are related to: (1) the typically-low concentration of the metals of interest (making their recovery cost-prohibitive), (2) the additional presence of economically-irrelevant metals, inorganics and organics, which can be present in far superior concentrations to the metals of interest (3) the high ionic strength, temperatures, and pressure of some of these matrices, complicating extraction, (4) the availability of existing techniques to remove the metals from the matrix but geared to meeting discharge limits and environmental regulations, and (5) the unavailability of technology targeting recovery (i.e., into marketable products), that can be integrated within existing processing chains in a sustainable manner (Dominguez-Benetton et al., 2018). Therefore, the ability to recover metals from geothermal brines relies on the discovery, understanding, and improvement of new processes that meet these challenges.

Different technologies have been investigated at the state of the art for metal removal from aqueous matrices, like biological treatments, membrane processes, advanced oxidations, chemical and electrochemical methods. More conventional methods include ion exchange, reduction, oxidation, solvent extraction, precipitation, electro-driven separations, and adsorption (Crini, 2005). Physicochemical treatments are the best available technology for recovery purposes, but they present important limitations. Adsorption processes are considered the most suitable option, due to low cost, safety, recyclability and efficiency (Samiey, Cheng, & Wu, 2014) but they have the disadvantage of lack of selectivity and low metal sorption capacity, thus and important amount of the metal content is typically disregarded. The second biggest disadvantage is that the adsorbed metal ions typically remain unchanged, implying that the economic value of the marketable metals remains low, whereas transformation into more valuable forms add to the economic profitability of the recovery process. For this purpose, reactive electrochemical methods are advantageous.

Electrochemical recovery of metals can be done by direct electrolysis, electro dialysis, electrocoagulation and capacitive deionization. In fact, some of these options already provide the only cost-effective way to obtain certain materials (e.g., there are no alternative technologies for most compounds obtained by electrowinning, such as aluminium, fluorine, and caustic soda). The contemporary demand of critical and strategic raw metals conveys the occasion to improve existing- or to develop breakthrough-electrochemical alternatives to tap the metal content of geothermal brines. Yet, the new alternatives will require high performance and low operational costs, as well as robustness to be applied individually or combined, to a broad range of geothermal brine compositions.

2.3. The GDEx technology

Recently, a new electrochemical process has been developed at VITO (Flemish Institute for Technological Research, Belgium) by Xochitl Dominguez-Benetton, named gas-diffusion electrocrystallization (GDEx). This technology removes metal and metalloid ions from liquid matrices (e.g., aqueous, organic, etc.), transforming them into amorphous or crystalline (micro- and nano-) precipitates which can be easily recovered by sedimentation or equivalent methods (Figure 2.2). GDEx is driven by a rapid one-pot reaction precipitation process, electrochemically-steered at the three-phase boundary between a porous gas-diffusion electrode, a liquid electrolyte and a gas.

By varying the operational parameters of GDEx (i.e., pH, ionic strength, metal/metalloid ion concentration, gas composition, electrochemical potential, etc.), not only compositional selectivity can be tuned but also other important properties of the product are controlled, such as morphology, stoichiometry, redox state, particle size, crystallite size, lattice parameter (Dominguez Benetton et al., 2015). This results, in turn, in the possibility to manipulate important properties of the material such as the magnetic susceptibility and reactivity, among others. GDEx has been already applied to remove certain metals from synthetic aqueous solutions, for example rare earth elements like Ce^{3+} , forming cerium oxide (cubic), or La^{3+} , forming sodium lanthanum carbonate (remondite). It has also been effective to obtain nanoparticles containing Cu, Al, Co, Cs, Li, and Zn, among others, mostly in the form of oxides, hydroxides, or carbonates. However, elemental Pt and Pd, have also been obtained, when using CO_2 as the oxidant gas (PLATIRUS project: Horizon 2020 TOPIC SC5-13-2016 grant agreement n° 730224). The process is not only effective for metals but also for metalloids. For example, the formation of borax can occur when boric acid is supplied. This is of special interest as borates are within those materials considered as critical for the EU and a number of geothermal fluids contain them. GDEx has also been applied dilute mixed metal solutions with high salinities (e.g. 30 g L^{-1}). GDEx is also effective to immobilize arsenic in the form of highly crystalline and stable scorodite. Its universality and easy scalability, as well as selectivity and the possibility to tailor crystallite properties, this method could be considered a breakthrough in both the field of removal and recovery of metals and metalloids from aqueous matrices, as well as in the synthesis of bare inorganic crystalline nanoparticles (Oceanit-Laboratories, 1990).

Figure 2.2. General scheme of the gas-diffusion electrocrystallization (GDEx) concept. An oxidant gas, provided through the gas compartment of the electrochemical cell (left), is electrochemically reduced at the triple-phase contact of the gas-diffusion cathode (1). The products of the electrochemical reduction of the oxidant gas react with the metal ions in solution (M^{n+}) and provide the decisive pH and redox potential conditions to form inorganic nano-crystallites which may remain in a stable colloidal dispersion (2). The nano-crystallites formed aggregate into nanoparticles (3), which may eventually sediment to be further recovered as powders (4).

2.4. Objectives and role of Task 3.2 within the CHPM2030 project

Task 3.2 within CHPM2030 focused on the extraction of metals from geothermal brines via the GDEx technology. As the characteristics of geothermal brines are variable, the GDEx system was operated using varied geothermal brines compositions (i.e., synthetic and real brines), and under different operational conditions (i.e., working electrode potential, temperature, salinity). After the GDEx treatment, the effluent containing mainly the salts that have not precipitated, is expected to follow a reverse electrodialysis process (Task 3.3) wherein the “osmotic energy” from the salinity gradient between the GDEx effluent and a lower salinity stream, will be used to generate electricity.

The key points of investigation in Task 3.2, were:

- (1) Key characteristics of geothermal brines relevant for GDEx metal recovery.
- (2) Concepts for the development of a selective, highly efficient and negligible-electricity-consuming metal recovery process (i.e., GDEx):
 - Calculations of thermodynamic equilibria in aqueous solutions for mixed metal matrices in ambient pressure processing conditions.
 - Characteristics of the porous cathodes and anode materials to be employed.
 - Physicochemical conditions of the electrolyte (simulated or real geothermal fluid) such as applied potential, pH, T, mixed metal composition, presence of other elements (especially silica), oxidant gas composition, flow conditions of the electrolyte and oxidant gas).
 - Characterization of mechanistic and kinetic features (electrochemical response, characterization of metal removal and recovery, characteristics of the solid precipitates and crystals formed).

The effect of the presence of metal-containing flowing carbon particles and their regeneration through GDEx was originally conceived. However, due to the characteristics of the particles synthesized for this purpose, and the results obtained within WP2, this concept is considered unfeasible for application in the geothermal systems issue of this project, as the particles produced (μ -sized) thus far would clog the pores of the reservoir and the electrochemical cell, when used in the required concentrations. Alternatively, the integration of the GDEx cathodic process with microbial anodes is considered, as this is expected to result in lower energy consumption and potentially additional power generation, under certain operational conditions.

(3) Generation of design criteria to improve process performance and control

- Framework of conditions of applicability of the technology to the removal and recovery of the metal content of geothermal fluids (expected i.e., hundreds to thousands of m^3 per day, inlet pH between 2 and 3, high salinity in the range of $30\text{--}300 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ NaCl equivalents, highly diluted metal content in ppm range).
- Establishment of reactor design criteria for further scalability.
- Process simulations based on experimental data to increase the knowledge of the process.
- Mass and energy balances (model compositions and real geothermal fluids).

3 Literature review on geothermal brines characterization

A literature survey was completed, regarding geothermal brines, to identify relevant characteristics and compounds of interest (i.e., metals, rare earth elements) that can be potentially recovered using the GDEX technology. The information obtained is summarized in Annex 1. A brief summary of the most relevant findings is presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Metal concentrations of specific elements of interest in geothermal brines.

ANIONS (ppm)	
Chlorides [Cl ⁻]	1,062–120,500
Carbonates [CO ₃ ⁻]	19.5–2,765
Sulphates [SO ₄ ⁻²]	10.6–31,380
CATIONS (ppm)	
Sodium [Na ⁺]	0.5–64,000
METALS OF INTEREST	
Lithium [Li ⁺]	5.6–250
Aluminium [Al ⁺]	0.4–6
Manganese [Mn ²⁺]	0.038–1,500
Iron [Fe ²⁺]	0.07–1,300
Zinc [Zn ²⁺]	0.018–500

Due to their high presence and the interest on their recovery, Li⁺ and Al⁺ were selected as a case study for extended experimental testing (see Chapter 7). It has been demonstrated that these two elements can be combined for the synthesis of Li-Al layered double hydroxyl-chlorides (LDH) (Besserguenev et al., 1997; Gupta, Agarwal, & Banerjee, 2012; Thomas & Kamath, 2002). LDHs are of special interest as they present physicochemical properties that make them suitable for a broad range of applications, particularly in catalysis, ion exchange, adsorption, CO₂ capture, photochemistry, drug delivery, etc. (Gupta et al., 2012; Huang et al., 2014; Paranthaman et al., 2017). Obtaining this kind of compounds by GDEX would provide a new route to synthesize them, which can be valorised independently of the application in geothermal systems.

4 Experimental set-up: Overview of the GDEx process and operational conditions

4.1. Experimental setup

Experiments were conducted in a flow-by three-chamber electrochemical cell. Platinum (10 cm²) was used as a counter anode, and a gas diffusion (GD) electrode (using compressed air 200 ml min⁻¹) of the same size was used as the working cathode.

Component choices for the GDEx system

Anode

For the experimental studies conducted in CHPM2030, the choice of anode materials was initially irrelevant, as the electrochemical system was always operated in a three-electrode configuration. The motivation for this was to have an appropriate control of the conditions to investigate thoroughly the gas-diffusion cathode, which is the main electrode of interest for metal recovery by GDEx. Thus, platinum/iridium 97%/3% was selected as counter anode material, due to their stability and durability under the operational conditions employed. Nevertheless, this anode choice would be unaffordable for practical purposes. Instead, dimensionally stable anodes aka DSA, made of Ti/TiO₂ or similar materials could be employed. Either the oxygen evolution or the chlorine evolution reactions would take place at the anode, which could be eventually recovered as by-products. Still, DSA are relatively expensive. Alternatively, microbial electrochemical reactions could be of interest (Dominguez-Benetton et al., 2018) not only because they are supported on inexpensive carbon materials, but because they have a positive impact on energy consumption and they are a more environmentally-friendly option. Preliminary testing coupling two halotolerant bioanodes to the gas-diffusion cathodes was performed as a proof of concept, and is shown further in the results section.

As the anode materials are not the priority for CHPM2030 at the current TLR levels, the choice for gas-diffusion electrodes is discussed more extensively.

Cathode

Activated carbon was the material of choice for the hydrophilic component of the gas-diffusion electrodes, due to: (1) its high ratio of pore volume combined with optimal distribution of pore volume, which result in a high degree of activation; (2) a high internal catalytic area, which results into a higher availability of reactive sites; (3) abundant presence of macropores, to enable transport to and from the catalytic surface; (4) featuring of hydrophilic and/or hydrophobic groups on the pore surface, which enable transport paths for both the aqueous and the gas phase for reaching the active sites (triple-phase boundary); and (5) high abundancy of functional groups, whose surface chemistry influences transport and interactions of reactants, acting as the active catalytic sites.

VITO's cold-rolled (VITO CoRe[®]) gas-diffusion electrodes were manufactured, given the knowledge and expertise acquired throughout the years on their fabrication (Alvarez-Gallego et al., 2012; Srikanth et al., 2016).

Other carbon materials were tested, for instance graphite, mixtures of activated carbon and Vulcan, or acetylene black, but it was concluded that activated carbon provides a better performance for the oxygen reduction reaction to hydrogen peroxide (which is the first reaction of interest to conduct the GDEx

process). In particular, Norit SX1G (Cabot) resulted in the highest current efficiencies, highest H_2O_2 concentrations produced, and it is cost effective. In addition, the different electrode materials assessed were also evaluated with a 4% loading of catalyst, i.e., CeO_2 nanoparticles which have proven highly effective for the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR). The incorporation of the catalyst resulted in higher current efficiencies (i.e., selectivity), but the cost of the catalyst is not justified by this improvement. Thus, ordinary Norit SX1G was employed. This material is acid washed, steam activated AC, with a specific surface area SSA_{BET} of $1000 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ (PDS), it has mean pore sizes of d_{50} $25 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, and d_{90} : $90 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, it is a high purity material, i.e., $<10 \text{ ppm Cu}$; $<200 \text{ ppm Fe}$; $<200 \text{ ppm Ca}$; $0.1\% \text{ Cl}$, and it has a very high adsorptive capacity. At present, it is possible to produce VITO CoRe[®] electrodes in-house, in a semi-automated way. Recently, the process to achieve up to 1 m^2 of electrode surface area was developed, setting the first milestone towards the feasibility for scaling-up electrochemical gas-diffusion-mediated processes.

The anodic and cathodic compartments were separated by a Zirfon membrane (ion-permeable separator). Two glass bottles (250 ml) contained the anolyte and catholyte (i.e., simulated/real geothermal brines), separately. The fluids were pumped at 40 ml min^{-1} through the reactor. The experimental setup is represented in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1. Schematic diagram of the GDEX technology for the treatment of geothermal brines.

At the GD cathode, the gas flowing in the gas chamber (i.e., air containing oxygen) is able to diffuse through the electrode and reach the catholyte at the three-phase boundaries. During the process, oxygen is electrochemically reduced at the cathode, forming peroxides (or polyatomic ions of the reduced gas), driving the crystallization or precipitation of composites between the metal ions and the oxidant-gas-reduction-product at the electrochemical interface. The precipitate is subsequently released into the aqueous electrolyte where it remains stable in a colloidal form during a certain period, but ultimately aggregates and precipitates. The starting pH of the catholyte is 3 (e.g., except when treating real geothermal brines that would be the pH of the sample) and it rises to a final value of 11.2 during the experiments. Standard conditions of the experiments are summarised in the table below.

Table 4.1. Standard conditions for the GDEX process unless is specified

Parameter	Unit	Value
Electrolyte volume	ml (each)	250
Electrolyte flow	ml min ⁻¹	40
Gas flow	ml min ⁻¹	200
Starting pH (in anolyte and catholyte)		3.0
Final pH (in catholyte)		11.2
Working electrode potential (Ewe)	V (vs Ag/AgCl)	-0.350
Temperature	°C	20
Salinity of supporting electrolyte	g L ⁻¹ NaCl	30

4.2. Sample preparation and analysis

The chemical reagents used to prepare the different solutions described throughout this deliverable are summarised in the table below.

Table 4.2. Chemical reagents used to prepare the solutions

Element	Chemical reagent	Specifications
Cl	NaCl	Acros Organics, China
Ca	CaCl ₂ *2H ₂ O	VWR Prolabo Chemicals, Belgium
Mg	MgCl ₂ *6H ₂ O	Merck, Germany
Fe	FeCl ₂ *4H ₂ O	Merck, Germany
Al	AlCl ₃	Merck, Germany
Cu	CuCl ₂ *2H ₂ O	Merck, Germany
Li	LiCl	Sigma-Aldrich, USA

The metal concentration in the liquid samples was determined in axial view, using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES, Agilent, 5100), equipped with a baffled cyclonic spray chamber and a conical nebulizer. 1 mL samples were taken during the experiment at pH values in the catholyte of 3 (initial), 5, 7, 9 and 11.2 (final). 0.45 µm filters (Millipore, USA) were used to filter all liquid samples before ICP analysis.

In addition, the X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) patterns of the precipitate were obtained with a diffractometer (Empyrean, Malvern Panalytical, United Kingdom) using CoK α radiation ($\lambda=1.7928 \text{ \AA}$) with 40 mA-45 kV and a finer step size of 0.013° 2 θ in the same scan range.

5 Evaluation of the effect of the temperature (20°C and 50°C) when treating three different simulated geothermal brines using the GDEx process

5.1. Introduction

The project considers to implement the GDEx technology to recover metals from geothermal brines which have a typical temperatures up to ~70°C, considering the study elaborated during the Work Package (WP) 2.4 (Figure 5.1).

Figure 5.1. The change of critical temperature range (°C) throughout the CHPM technology loop.

At present, given the experimental setups available, the GDEx process can be operated only up to ~70°C without electrolyte losses (thus the range indicated in Figure 5). However, if future design optimizations are made and some materials are replaced, the GDEx process could be operated at higher temperatures and even in pressurized vessels, being therefore in operational conditions more suited to the CHPM cycle. At present, reliable experiments for the purpose of this project were conducted up to 50°C.

Temperature can not only affect product formation (e.g., composition, morphology, structure, etc.) during GDEx operation, but also the performance of the electrochemical process, as kinetics and activation energy of the reactions taking place on the surface of the electrode and in the bulk solution are susceptible to these variations (Divisek et al., 1994). It has been reported that increasing the temperature of the electrolyte, electrochemical reaction kinetics are increased, thus enhancing the electrochemical oxidation/reduction processes (Divisek et al., 1994; Schmidt, Grgur, Markovic, & Ross, 2001). Therefore, the effect of the temperature for the GDEx treatment of three different basal geothermal brines was evaluated.

5.2. Methodology

Simulated geothermal brines

Based on the information obtained from the literature survey, three geothermal brine compositions were selected for general testing by the GDEX system. Their compositions have been simulated in the laboratory and are summarised in the Table 5.1 (Hardardóttir et al., 2009; V. Hardardottir, Hannington, Hedenquist, Kjarsgaard, & Hoal, 2010; Vidgdis Hardardottir, 2011; Smedley, Bromley, Shepherd, Edmunds, & Kay, 1989). The composition was limited only to a few metals, as the aim was mostly focused on understanding the effect of salinity, presence of calcium and magnesium, which are ubiquitous in geothermal brines. For this reason we refer to these as basal geothermal brines. The choice of the metals for these simulations was due to their more relevant concentrations for each type of brine.

Table 5.1. Simulated basal geothermal brine compositions

		England	Iceland	Belgium
NaCl	g L⁻¹	5	30	135
Ca	ppm	1000	1750	10000
Mg	ppm	50	5	600
Fe	ppm	0	50	800
Al	ppm	180	0	0
Cu	ppm	0	15	0

Experimental conditions

To study the effect of temperature on the performance of the GDEX technology, the system was operated at two different temperatures, 20°C (room temperature) and 50°C with each of the simulated basal geothermal brines (Table 5.1.). The experimental setup and operational parameters are described in Section 4.

5.3. Results

GDEX products obtained from simulated geothermal brines at different temperatures (20°C and 50°C)

As it can be seen from Figure 5.2, observing the different colour of the obtained samples, it can be deduced that when operating at different temperatures different precipitate compositions are formed.

Figure 5.2. Precipitates formed during the GDEx treatment of three different simulated geothermal brines at two different temperatures.

The analysis of the obtained products was carried out with XRD (X-Ray diffraction), the compounds in the precipitates have been identified and the results are summarised in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2. XRD results obtained for the precipitates formed during the GDEx treatment of three different simulated geothermal brines at two different temperatures

	Iceland	England	Belgium
Experiment at 20°C	Copper Chloride Hydroxide $\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}(\text{OH})_3$ Copper Chloride Hydroxide Hydrate $\text{Cu}(\text{OH},\text{Cl})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Aluminum Hydroxide $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$	Calcium Iron Chloride Hydroxide Hydrate $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_6\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ Magnesium Hydroxide $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$
Experiment at 50°C	Copper Chloride Hydroxide $\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}(\text{OH})_3$ Iron Oxide Fe_3O_4	Aluminium Hydroxide $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ Calcium carbonate CaCO_3 Aluminium Oxide Hydroxide $\text{AlO}(\text{OH})$ Magnesium Aluminium Hydroxide carbonate $((\text{Mg}_4\text{Al}_2)(\text{OH})_{12}(\text{CO}_3)(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3)_{0.5}$	Calcium Iron Chloride Hydroxide Hydrate $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_6\text{Cl}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ Magnesium Hydroxide $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ Calcium Carbonate CaCO_3 Iron Oxide Fe_3O_4

From the XRD results, it can be observed that at higher temperatures a broader variety of products is obtained than at 20°C. This can be due to the improved solubility of salts with the temperature, which in turn enhances the rate of electrochemical reactions and contributes to the formation of different products.

Furthermore, dynamic light scattering (DLS) analyses showed that mainly large, polydisperse flocks are formed. For the sample of England, the higher size of the obtained particles and their degree of polydispersity make the sample not suitable for this analysis. In addition, while in the case of Iceland variations in temperature do not strongly affect the particle size of the product formed, for the sample from Belgium, size and polydispersity considerably decrease as temperature increases (Table 5.3).

Table 5.3. DLS results obtained for the precipitates formed during the GDEx treatment of three different simulated geothermal brines at two different temperatures

		Iceland	England	Belgium
Experiment at 20°C	Polydispersity	High (0.477)	Not relevant	High (0.580)
	Mean particle size	>1 µm (1587 nm)	Not relevant	>1 µm (1683 nm)
Experiment at 50°C	Polydispersity	High (0.439)	High (0.474)	High (0.509)
	Mean particle size	>1 µm (1502 nm)	>1 µm (1956 nm)	200 nm

Operational performance and energy balances

As salts present in the bulk solution could precipitate on the surface of the electrode, affecting its performance during the experiments, the resistance of the electrode has been measured before and after the experiments to compare the effect of temperatures on scaling in the GDEx system. From Figure 5.3, it can be observed that the increase of the electrode resistance during the experiments is smaller when operating at higher temperatures. This tendency can be linked to the higher solubility of the salts at higher temperatures, avoiding its precipitation on the surface of the electrode, thus affecting performance.

Experiment at 20°C

Experiment at 50°C

Figure 5.3. Resistance of the working electrode (GD cathode) before and after the experiments developed at 20 and 50°C using three different simulated geothermal brines (i.e., Iceland, England and Belgium).

It has also been observed that higher values of the current and shorter treatment times are achieved when operating rather at higher temperatures or increasing the salt content (i.e., as for Belgium brines). In addition, higher metal content results in longer process times (Figure 5.4.)

Experiment at 20°C

Experiment at 50°C

Figure 5.4. Observed current during experiments developed at 20 and 50°C using three different simulated geothermal brines (i.e., Iceland, England and Belgium).

For all the experiments, energy consumption and efficiency was calculated and results are summarised in the table below (Table 5.4).

Table 5.4. Energy balance of the GDEx treatment of three different simulated geothermal brines at two different temperatures

	Experiment at 20°C			Experiment at 50°C		
	Iceland	England	Belgium	Iceland	England	Belgium
Energy used (kWh m ⁻³)	0.19	0.96	2.10	0.09	1.15	1.96
Energy used (kWh kg ⁻¹ metal rem.)	2.1	11.4	3.4	5.17	26.4	11.5
Current efficiency (%)	97	99	81	< 20	< 20	< 45

It can be observed that the energy usage per volume of water treated (i.e., kWh m⁻³) increases at 20°C for the brines of Iceland (53%), and Belgium (7%), while decreases for the sample of England (20%). As the volume of sample is the same in all cases (i.e., 250 mL), variations in the energy consumed per unit of volume treated are related to a higher presence of metals (i.e., Fe, Al and Cu) and manganese in the sample, as it is higher for Belgium and lower for Iceland. Depending on the amount of precipitate obtained from each experiment, the energy consumed per kilogram of material recovered (i.e., kWh kg⁻¹ metal removed) was calculated, and also the current efficiency (%), which represents the amount of energy that has been consumed by the system in the electrochemical reactions to precipitate the metals in the solution. It can be observed that the amount of energy increases with the temperature, and obtained values for the current efficiency are lower at 50°C. This tendency can be caused by the higher solubility of metallic salts at 50°C, and therefore the lower precipitation rates are achieved.

5.4. Conclusions

The following conclusions can be drawn from the GDEx experiments carried out with the three simulated geothermal brines at different temperatures:

- Different metal-containing products can be formed at different temperatures, with a broader variety of compounds at higher temperatures.
- The precipitates formed are mainly composed of large, polydisperse flocks. However, results suggest that higher temperatures favors the formation of smaller particles.
- The increase in electrode resistance during the GDEx treatment is smaller when operating at higher temperatures.
- Higher salt content and higher temperatures result in higher current densities and shorter process time.
- Higher metal content results in longer process time.
- Energy consumption per unit of weight of product increases and current efficiency decreases when operating at higher temperatures

Finally, it is necessary to point out that as the experimental setup was not initially designed for being used at higher temperatures, it may present several operational limitations that affect the energy calculations performed in this section.

6 Evaluation of the long term performance of GDEx for the treatment of three different simulated geothermal brines

6.1. Introduction

When considering the GDEx technology to be implemented for the treatment of geothermal brines and high temperatures, the main limitations of the system could be mainly attributed to the precipitation of salts on the surface of the electrode, corrosion of the electrode, and leakages of the fluid from the reactor. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the long term performance of the GDEx technology, operating at high temperatures (i.e., in the most extreme conditions) in order to identify its limitations and define how to address them.

The long term performance of the GDEx system was evaluated for the treatment of three different geothermal brines (Table 5.1), and the obtained results are summarised below. These experiments focused on evaluating the performance of the GDEx technology, operating at high temperature (i.e., 50°C) during 10 days, in order to define the main limitations that the system present for its further potential scalability.

6.2. Methodology

The GDEx system was operated at 50°C during 10 consecutive days for the treatment of the three simulated geothermal brines described in Table 5.1. The xperimental setup and operational parameters, as well as brine compositions were similar to those described in Section 4 and Table 5.1, respectively.

6.3. Results

As stated before, the presence of salt content of the brines could affect the performance of the GDEx system as they can precipitate on the surface of the electrode. To evaluate this effect, the resistance of the electrode was measured before and after each trial and it is represented in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1. Resistance of the working electrode (GD cathode) before and after the long term performance experiments developed at 50°C during 10 days using three different simulated geothermal brines (i.e., Iceland, England and Belgium).

From Figure 6.1, it can be observed how the resistance of the electrode increases after 10-days of GDEx operation at 50°C, which indicates that the GD cathode is being altered throughout the experiment, affecting

the performance of the system. In addition, comparing these results with those obtained at 50°C during short term performance of the GDEx system (Figure 5.3), it can be deduced that the longer the reactor operates, the higher the resistance of the cathode. Particularly for the case of Iceland, the resistance after the long-term experiment increases considerably, attributable to calcium precipitation.

Figure 6.2 shows a picture of the GD cathode before and after the experiments with each different geothermal brine. The pictures in the bottom of the Figure are SEM images of the corresponding electrodes.

Figure 6.2. Working electrode surface before and after the experiments: In the top, a picture of the electrode, in the bottom, SEM images of the electrode surface.

It can be observed that abundant mineral fouling has been formed on the surface of the working electrodes during the experiments. Its composition varies depending on the characteristics of the influent and operational parameters in each trial, however the Energy-Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDS) spectrum showed that the main components of the fouling correspond to Ca, Mg, Na, and Cl, but not the metals (Figure 6.3). This indicates that the metals are not precipitating on the surface of the electrode but they can be recovered as a precipitate in the bulk solution. In addition, the results suggest that when operating the reactor during longer periods, it would be convenient to alternate cleaning cycles of the electrode in order to increase the performance and the durability of the system.

Figure 6.3. EDS spectrum of GD cathode and precipitated products. (A) Initial GD cathode, and after the treatment of simulated brines from (B) England, (C) Iceland, and (D) Belgium.

6.4. Conclusions

After operating the GDEx system at high temperature (i.e., 50°C) for the treatment of three simulated geothermal brines during long term of continuous operation (i.e., 10 days), it was observed mineral scaling on the surface of the working electrode, that may affect the performance of the electrochemical system. An increase in the resistance of the electrode before and after the experiment was detected. Therefore, alternating cleaning cycles of the electrode would be recommended to increase its performance in the long term. In addition, the precipitated fouling was mainly formed by salts containing Ca, Mg, Na and Cl, but not the metals in the composition, which can be recovered as a precipitate in the bulk solution.

7 Li/Al LDH synthesis with GDEx

7.1. Introduction

From the literature review described in Section 3, Li and Al have been selected to study metal recovery using the GDEx process. It has been demonstrated that these two elements can be combined for the synthesis of Li-Al layered double hydroxides (LDHs); however, the feasibility of doing this with GDEx is unknown.

LDHs are of high interest as they present specific physicochemical properties that make them suitable for a broad range of applications, particularly in catalysis, energy storage, ion exchange, adsorption, CO₂ capture, photochemistry, etc. Amongst LDHs, Li/Al LDH synthesis is of special significance for the following reasons: (1) Li/Al LDHs are the only example of a M(I),M(III) cation pair LDH (Bellotto et al., 1996; Besserguenev et al., 1997; Carlos J. Serna, Joe L. White, 1977; Serna, Rendon, & Iglesias, 1982); (2) Li/Al LDHs are the only ones that present long-range ordering (Besserguenev et al., 1997; Carlos J. Serna, Joe L. White, 1977; Serna et al., 1982). Order has been demonstrated within each layer, but the random stacking of the layers occurs (Thiel, Chiang, & Poepfelmeier, 1993); and (3) LiAl LDH undergo facile anion exchange and present a higher degree of size selectivity (Sissoko, Iyagba, Sahai, & Biloen, 1985), making them suitable materials for cost-effective and eco-friendly separation processes.

Therefore this section focuses on the study of the performance of the GDEx process for the recovery of these metals under different operational conditions (i.e., Li:Al ratio, working electrode potential, salinity, temperature, and presence of Ca and Mg).

7.2. Methodology

Experiments have been performed using the experimental setup described in Section 4 and the standard conditions summarised in Table 4.1. Different parameters (Table 7.1) were varied separately to determine how do they affect the GDEx process performance and product formation.

Table 7.1. Parameters varied during the experiments using GDEx for Li/Al recovery

Parameter	Standard values used during all experiments unless specified	Parameters varied for this study
Li:Al ratio	1:1 (40 ppm : 155.9 ppm)	0:1, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 2:1
Working electrode potential (Ewe vs Ag/AgCl)	-0.350 V	-0.350 V, -0.700 V, -0.900 V
Salinity of electrolytes [NaCl]	30 g L ⁻¹	5 g L ⁻¹ , 30 g L ⁻¹ , 75 g L ⁻¹ , 135 g L ⁻¹
Presence of Ca and Mg	Ca] = 0 ppm [Mg] = 0 ppm	[Ca] = 2000 ppm and 15000 ppm [Mg] = 100 ppm and 1000 ppm
Temperature	20°C (room temperature)	20°C and 50°C

7.3. Results

Preliminary experiments

Initial trial experiments only included either Al (155.9 ppm), or Li (40 ppm), independently. While for Li alone there was no precipitate observed, for Al alone it was observed that at pH 7 a precipitate formed in the catholyte compartment (Figure 7.1). However the precipitate re-dissolved when pH rose up to 11.

These results can be explained from the Pourbaix diagram for Li and Al (Figure 7.2, i.e., theoretical thermodynamic equilibria in aqueous solutions).

When combining both elements in the solution the precipitate formed at pH 7 was not then re-dissolved at pH 11 (Figure 7.1.)

Figure 7.1. Pictures of the precipitate formed and re-dissolved during experiments with Al and Li addition.

Figure 7.2. Potential-pHequilibrium diagram (Pourbaix) for (A) the system aluminium-water, and (B) the system lithium-water.

From these results, experiments combining Li and Al were developed under different operational conditions, as reported in this section.

Experiments at different Li:Al ratios

- Effect of Li addition

Experiments using the same initial concentration of Al but an increasing concentration of Li were developed. Table 7.2 summarises the initial concentrations of Li and Al used on each independent trial.

Table 7.2. Li and Al concentrations using during the experiments to study the effect of Li addition.

Li:Al ratio	0:1	0.5:1	1:1	2:1
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Al	ppm	155.9	155.9	155.9	155.9
Li	ppm	0	20	40	80

Figure 7.3 illustrates the evolution of pH during the experiments, as a function of the electric charge applied. A plateau at pH 4.5 is observed; related to the precipitation of a product containing both Al and Li. In addition, for the experiment only using Al (i.e., red line), a larger second plateau is observed at pH 9.5 linked to the product that is formed and subsequently re-dissolved. This second plateau can be also recognised when Li is supplemented to an Al-only-containing solution; however, this is considerably smaller than for the latter case. This can be explained due to impurities of an Al product (i.e., aluminium hydroxide) that is in formed in excess and re-dissolved at higher pH.

Figure 7.3. pH evolution during experiments to study the effect of Li addition.

In addition, it can be noticed that the increase in the concentration of Li in the treated catholyte does not affect considerably the charge used to form the precipitate during the experiments.

The formed precipitate was analysed using XRD, and lithium aluminium chloride hydroxide hydrate (i.e., Li/Al LDH) and impurities of aluminium hydroxide were obtained (Figure 7.4).

Figure 7.4. XRD analysis of the solid produced during experiments at different Li:Al ratios when increasing Li initial concentration.

Li/Al LDH are of special interest due to the particularities they show amongst other mixed-metals LDHs: (1) Li/Al LDHs is the only example of a M(I),M(III) cation pair LDH (Bellotto et al., 1996; Besserguenev et al., 1997; Carlos J. Serna, Joe L. White, 1977; Serna et al., 1982); (2) Li/Al LDHs are the only ones that present long-range ordering (Besserguenev et al., 1997; Carlos J. Serna, Joe L. White, 1977; Serna et al., 1982); and (3) LiAl LDH undergoes facile anion exchange and presents higher degree of size selectivity (Sissoko et al., 1985) which makes it a suitable material for cost-effective and eco-friendly material in separation science. While the II-III LDHs are prepared by a co-precipitation reaction, the Li-Al LDHs are generally prepared by hydrothermal conditions by prolonged heating with less yield (Gupta et al., 2012). GDEx represents an alternative approach to synthesise Li/Al LDHs and offers the potential to control its structural properties (i.e., interlayer distance, composition, anion intercalation) and therefore its physic-chemical properties (i.e., adsorption and anion exchange capacity) through adjusting the operational parameters of the process.

In addition, from the XRD diagram, it can be noticed that the peaks corresponding to the Li/Al LDH are better defined at the Li:Al ratio of 1:1, indicating a higher level of purity, and therefore this ratio will be used further in the experiments.

A mass balance of the metals in the electrolyte and the precipitated solid has been done and the percentage of metals recovered in the final product is represented in Figure 7.5.

Figure 7.5. Percentage (%) of the initial metal recovered in the precipitated product at different pH and initial Li concentration: (1) Li:Al 0:1, (2) Li:Al 0.5:1, (3) Li:Al 1:1, and (4) Li:Al 2:1.

It can be observed that at pH 9 the maximum amount of Al can be recovered in all the experiments (up to 100%), while if continuing increasing the pH, impurities of aluminium hydroxide can be re-dissolved and therefore not present in the solid. The product obtained at pH 11 contains a higher percentage of Li, and the Li/Al LDH formed is more pure at this pH. Therefore, a balance between quantity and quality needs to be considered at this stage, we can recover a higher amount of solid product with more impurities at pH 9, or more pure Li/Al LDH at pH 11, but less Al will be recovered in the latest scenario.

- Effect of Al addition

In the next set of experiments, the concentration of Li remains constant while two different Al concentrations are being used in the experiments to study the effect of Al addition (Table 7.3).

Table 7.3. Li and Al concentrations used during the experiments to study the effect of Al addition

Li:Al ratio		1:2	1:3
Al	ppm	155.9	233.9
Li	ppm	20	20

As it was observed before, two plateaus were formed, a longer one at pH around 4.5 and one less pronounced at pH 9.5. However, while when in Figure 7.3 all the lines are superposed, indicating that Li addition does not affect the charge consumed during the experiments, when Al concentration is higher in the experiment, the consumed charge also increases (Figure 7.6). This suggests that the incorporation of the Al into the Li/Al LDH, and the formation of aluminium hydroxide impurities, require the incorporation of electrons during the process and therefore charge consumption.

Figure 7.6. pH evolution during experiments to study the effect of Al addition.

The formed precipitate was also analysed using XRD, and Li/Al LDH and impurities of aluminium hydroxide were obtained (Figure 7.7).

Figure 7.7. XRD analysis of the solid produced during experiments at different Li:Al ratios when increasing Al initial concentration.

From the XRD diagrams obtained, it can be concluded that the higher amount of Al present in the sample, the more impurities of aluminium hydroxide are formed, reducing the purity of the LDH product.

According to the results presented before, the mass balance represented in the Figure 7.8 showed that at pH 9 recovery of Al achieved the higher value, while at pH 11, precipitated impurities of aluminium hydroxide can be re-dissolved and therefore not recovered in the solid. On the other hand, the obtained solid at pH 11 would present an enhanced purity of Li/Al LDH.

Figure 7.8. Percentage (%) of the initial metal recovered in the precipitated product at different pH and initial Al concentration: (1) Li:Al 1:2, and (2) Li:Al 1:3.

The following SEM images of the product demonstrated the laminated structure of the formed particles, which corresponds to the structure of LDH compounds found in literature.

Figure 7.9. SEM images of the solid produced during experiments at different Li:Al ratios. Scalebar: 1 µm.

Table 7.4. Energy balance during experiments at different Li:Al ratios

	Experiment Li:Al	Energy used (kWh m ⁻³)	Energy used (kWh kg ⁻¹ metal rem.)	Current efficiency (%)
Effect of Li addition	0:1	0.13	31.75	43
	0.5:1	1.61	10.50	12
	1:1	1.63	10.10	13
	2:1	1.63	10.11	16
Effect of Al addition	1:2	1.61	10.50	12
	1:3	2.31	10.20	11

As the interest of this project is on the recovery of the metals from geothermal brines, the energy consumed by the experiments and the calculated current efficiency are summarised in Table 7.4.

Experiments at different working electrode potential

Electrochemical experiments applying different working electrode potentials (Ewe) were performed using the GDEx technology and a Li:Al ratio of 1:1 (i.e., selected from previous experiments). Figure 7.10 shows the pH vs charge graph where the same two plates identified before, in Figures 7.3 and 7.6, are represented (i.e., at pH 4.5 and pH 9.5). It can be observed that despite different Ewe used during experiments, the charge consumed by each of them is very similar, as all the lines are superposed.

Figure 7.10. pH evolution during experiments to study the effect of Ewe.

The precipitate formed in each experiment was analysed by XRD (Figure 7.11).

Figure 7.11. XRD analysis of the solid produced during experiments at different Ewe vs Ag/AgCl.

The XRD patterns obtained for the precipitates at the different applied potentials are very similar, from which it can be concluded that the same product is obtained. However more in deep research would be recommended to study how this operational parameter affects other properties of the obtained compound (structure, BET surface area, etc.).

From the results of the mass balance represented in Figure 7.12, and as it has been observed before (i.e., Figures 7.5 and 7.8), the best recovery is achieved at pH 9. A higher amount of Al remains as aluminium hydroxide, solid at this pH, and it re-dissolves when increasing the pH during the experiment.

Figure 7.12. Percentage (%) of the initial metal recovered in the precipitated product at different pH and Ewe vs Ag/AgCl: (1) -350 mV, (2) -700 mV, and (3) -900 mV.

SEM images represented in Figure 7.13 reveal that despite the Ewe applied during the experiments, the laminar structure of the product remains similar in all experiments.

Figure 7.13. SEM images of the solid produced during experiments at different Ewe. Scalebar: 1 µm.

The energy consumed during the experiments at different Ewe, and the current efficiency achieved at pH 9, are summarised in Table 7.5.

Table 7.5. Energy balance during experiments at different Ewe vs Ag/AgCl.

Experiment Ewe (mV)	Energy used (kWh m ⁻³)	Energy used (kWh kg ⁻¹ metal rem.)	Current efficiency (%)
-350	1.63	10.10	13
-700	3.43	22.32	36
-900	4.71	29.95	36

From the energy balance, it can be observed that the energy consumed per unit of volume of water treated and per unit of mass of recovered product increases with the applied Ewe, as well as the current efficiency. However, at the higher Ewe (i.e., -700 mV and -900 mV) this increase is not further continued. Therefore, -700 mV would be determined as a limiting Ewe. At -900 mV, hydrogen evolution is a competing process.

Experiments at different salinities

When increasing the salinity of the electrolyte (i.e., geothermal brines) the higher presence of ions in solution is expected to contribute to an increased transfer of ions, therefore enhancing the occurrence of reactions

at the electrode surface (i.e., mass transport improved by migration). The salinity of the simulated electrolyte is increased using a higher concentration of NaCl as electrolyte.

It can be observed from Figure 7.14, that when increasing the salinity of the electrolyte, the charge consumed during the process decreases, as the electrical resistance of the bulk solution become smaller.

Figure 7.14. pH evolution during experiments to study the effect of salinity.

Figure 7.15 shows the XRD patterns obtained for the precipitated samples obtained when evaluating the effect of salinity during GDEX operation.

Figure 7.15. XRD analysis of the solid produced during experiments at different salinities.

There are no significant differences between the XRD diagrams obtained for the samples when salinity is in the range 5-75 g L⁻¹ NaCl. The solid is mainly composed by Li/Al LDH and aluminium hydroxide. For the highest value of salinity (i.e., 135 g L⁻¹ NaCl), the main product corresponds to the Li/Al LDH alone; however the lower peaks obtained for this product reveal that its crystallinity is not as defined as for the solid obtained for the rest of experiments.

Same as before, the results obtained from the mass balance (Figure 7.16) shows that the higher removal of the metal content in the simulated geothermal brine of these experiments is at pH 9. And therefore the energy balance was performed when this value is achieved during the experiments (Table 7.6).

Figure 7.16. Percentage (%) of the initial metal recovered in the precipitated product at different pH and salinities: (1) 5 g L⁻¹ NaCl, (2) 30 g L⁻¹ NaCl, (3) 75 g L⁻¹ NaCl, and (4) 135 g L⁻¹ NaCl.

As it has been observed before, the laminar structure of the precipitated product is observed in the experiments developed using different salinities (Figure 7.17).

Figure 7.17. SEM images of the solid produced during experiments at different values of salinity. Scalebar: 1 μm.

Table 7.6 summarises the results obtained from the energy balance developed for these experiments.

Table 7.6. Energy balance during experiments at different salinities

Experiment [NaCl] (g L ⁻¹)	Energy used (kWh m ⁻³)	Energy used (kWh kg ⁻¹ metal rem.)	Current efficiency (%)
5	2.31	15.21	29
30	1.63	10.10	13
75	1.41	8.61	19
135	1.28	7.59	23

From table 7.6, Energy consumption during experiments performed at different salinity values shows that energy consumption decrease when increasing the salinity.

Experiments in the presence of Ca and Mg

Ca and Mg are conventionally found in geothermal brines. The presence of these salts can affect the performance of the system if they precipitate inside the reactor, particularly on the surface of the working electrode. With the purpose of evaluating the effect of the presence of these two elements during the GDEx process for the recovery of Li and Al, a series of experiments have been developed as summarised in Table 7.7.

Table 7.7. Experiments performed at different concentrations of Ca and Mg

Evaluated parameter	Experiment	[Ca] (ppm)	[Mg] (ppm)
Ca addition	1	0	0
	2	2000	0
	3	15000	0
Mg addition	4	0	100
	5	0	1000
	6	2000	100
	7	2000	1000

- Effect of Ca addition

The effect of Ca has been evaluated at two different concentrations (i.e., 2000 ppm and 15000ppm) and the results have been compared with those obtained without Ca in the solution. Figure 7.18 shows the graph pH vs charge. From the Figure, it can be observed that increasing the concentration of Ca, the charge consumed to form the precipitate increases as well. Furthermore, the second plateau that can be seen at 0 ppm of Ca no longer appears at the highest concentration used of this element, which suggest that the Al that was being re-dissolved, now has interact with the Ca in excess to form another compound that does not re-dissolve.

Figure 7.18. pH evolution during experiments to study the effect of Ca addition.

From the XRD analysis of the precipitated product it can be observed that Al and Ca have precipitated together as calcium aluminium oxide chloride hydrate, while aluminium hydroxide is not detected in the solid. For the highest concentration of Ca used during this experiments (i.e., 15000 ppm) calcium carbonate has been detected in the precipitate.

Figure 7.19. XRD analysis of the solid produced during experiments at different Ca concentrations.

A mass balance has been developed at different pH (Figure 7.20). And as it has been observed before, the precipitation, and therefore the recovery of the metals in the solution, is higher at pH 9.

Figure 7.20. Percentage (%) of the initial metal recovered in the precipitated product at different pH and Ca addition: (1) 0 ppm, (2) 2000 ppm, and (3) 15000 ppm.

- Effect of Mg addition

In Figure 7.21 pH evolution of experiments performed to study the effect of Mg addition are represented. Same tendency observed for Ca addition is obtained when increasing the concentration of Mg in the experiments. However, the charge consumption increase is more noticeable with the addition of Mg compared to Ca.

Figure 7.21. pH evolution during experiments to study the effect of Mg addition.

The XRD analysis of the solid precipitate during the experiments shows that Ca and Al again precipitate as calcium aluminium oxide chloride hydrate, but also two compounds more are formed when magnesium is present, magnesium aluminium hydroxide and magnesium hydroxide when using the higher concentrations of Mg in the solution (Figure 7.22).

Figure 7.22. XRD analysis of the solid produced during experiments at different Ca concentrations.

The mass balance in Figure 7.23 shows the same tendency observed in preliminary experiments, where the precipitation and recovery of the metals in the solution, is higher at pH 9. And therefore the energy balance has been developed at this pH (Table 7.8).

Figure 7.23. Percentage (%) of the initial metal recovered in the precipitated product at different pH and Mg addition: (1) 0 ppm, (2) 100 ppm Mg, (3) 1000 ppm Mg, (4) 100 ppm Mg + 2000 ppm Ca, and (5) 1000 ppm Mg + 2000 ppm Ca.

The energy consumed by these experiments and its current efficiency is summarised in Table 7.8.

Table 7.8. Energy balance during experiments at different Ca and Mg addition

Evaluated parameter	Experiment	[Ca] (ppm)	[Mg] (ppm)	Energy used (kWh m ⁻³)	Energy used (kWh kg ⁻¹ metal rem.)	Current efficiency (%)
Ca addition	1	0	0	1.63	10.10	13
	2	2000	0	2.97	19.04	8
	3	15000	0	2.59	15.39	10
Mg addition	4	0	100	2.28	12.61	17
	5	0	1000	12.19	66.21	3
	6	2000	100	3.08	17.23	14
	7	2000	1000	12.22	83.36	2

Experiment at different temperatures

Temperature is an important factor to be considered when working with geothermal brines and therefore it has also been considered as an operational parameter for the GDEx process. Experiments have been developed at two different temperatures, 20°C and 50°C for the recovery of Li and Al, and the results have been compared in this section.

Figure 7.24 shows the diagram pH vs charge for both experiments. It can be observed that when operating at higher temperature the length of the first plateau is slightly shorter and therefore the energy consumed to precipitate the products.

Figure 7.24. pH evolution during experiments to study the effect of the temperature.

XRD analysis of the obtained precipitate at different temperatures is represented in Figure 7.25.

Figure 7.25. XRD analysis of the solid produced during experiments at different temperature.

It can be observed from these results that at higher temperature Li/Al LDH has not been detected during the analysis as the graph perfectly fits the aluminium hydroxide patron. Lithium is precipitating in a product whose crystalline structure is detected as that of lithium hydride (LiH) by XRD. However, LiH is highly reactive in water and would be violently decomposed; thus, further investigations are needed to elucidate the nature of the product formed. The mass balance shows that metal recovery is highest at pH 9.

Figure 7.26. Percentage (%) of the initial metal recovered in the precipitated product at different pH and temperature: (1) 20°C and (2) 50°C.

As the highest amount of metals is recovered at pH 9, the energy balance has been developed at this value of pH and results are summarised in Table 7.9.

Table 7.9. Energy balance during experiments at different temperatures

Experiment Temperature (°C)	Energy used (kWh m ⁻³)	Energy used (kWh kg ⁻¹ metal rem.)	Current efficiency (%)
20	1.63	10.10	13
50	1.69	10.66	15

Results show that the energy consumed by unit of volume treated is very similar at both values of temperature. In addition, despite energy consumption per kg of metal precipitated is slightly higher at 50°C, which can be due to the higher solubility of metals at higher temperatures, the current efficiency is higher as more product has been recovered at 50°C.

7.4. Conclusions

The main conclusions that can be drawn from the results of the performance of the GDEx process for Li/Al recovery at different operational conditions are:

- Preliminary experiments for the recovery of Li and Al using the GDEx technology showed that: (1) Al alone precipitates at pH 5-7 and re-dissolves at pH 9-11, (2) Li alone does not precipitate, and (3) when Li and Al are combined during the process, a precipitate is formed at pH 5-7 that does not re-dissolve.
- The main products precipitated in the GDEx process when combining Li and Al are Li/Al LDH and impurities of aluminium hydroxide.
- Higher recovery rates of the metals (i.e., sum of Al and Li) are achieved at a pH 9, however the obtained product contains an increased amount of aluminium hydroxide impurities, which can be re-dissolved when leaving the process operate until pH 11, therefore enhancing the purity of the Li/Al LDH product obtained at higher pH.
- The incorporation of Li in the precipitated product does not require a consumption of electrons (charge) while the incorporation of Al does, spending more charge during the process when an excess of Al is present.
- Higher working electrode potential results in shorter process time but no increase in the charge consumption.
- Higher salt content results in higher current, shorter process time and an decrease in the energy consumption.
- The charge and the energy consumed by the process increases with the Ca and Mg concentration. This effect is more pronounced when increasing Mg concentration.
- While at 20°C Li/Al LDH and aluminium hydroxide were the main produced compounds in the precipitate, at 50°C the Li/Al LDH is not detected. Li is precipitating into a compound that shows the XRD pattern of lithium hydride (LiH), but since this product would reactively decompose in water, further investigations are needed to establish its true composition.
- Increasing the temperature from 20°C to 50°C, the energy consumption per kg of metal precipitated slightly increases, due to the higher solubility of metals at higher temperatures. However, the current efficiency is slightly enhanced at higher temperature.

Recovery of Li and Al and the production of Li/Al LDH has been demonstrated by GDEx process. However more in deep analysis is needed to evaluate its properties and how the varied parameters can affect them.

8 GDEx technology for the treatment of real geothermal brines

8.1. Introduction

To complete the study on the proof-of-concepts of using the GDEx technology for the recovery of metals from geothermal brines, experiments have been performed using a real matrix from Romania. Samples from two different sites were tested and results are described in this section.

8.2. Methodology

Real geothermal brines

Two different samples of geothermal brines from Romania were used as catholyte in the GDEx system. Characterization of the chemical content in the samples is summarised in Table 8.1, and the complete characterization of the sample can be found in Annex 2.

Table 8.1. Chemical characterization of main components found in real brines from Romania

Parameter	Units	Sample 1		Sample 2	
		Total	Filtered	Total	Filtered
pH		7.9		8.2	
Sulfate	mg L ⁻¹	1100	1100	60	59
Chloride	mg L ⁻¹	<5	<5	<5	<5
Ca	µg L ⁻¹	305000	303000	50900	50800
Mg	µg L ⁻¹	85600	85600	20500	20500
Sr	µg L ⁻¹	12040	12040	760	650
Li	µg L ⁻¹	129	129	33	33
Mn	µg L ⁻¹	40	39	<1	<1
Ba	µg L ⁻¹	32	32	81	81
Rb	µg L ⁻¹	16	16	14	14
As	µg L ⁻¹	9	3.8	5.7	5.7
Zn	µg L ⁻¹	1.5	2.9	62	62
Ni	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	13	12

Figure 8.1. Real geothermal brines from Romania: (A) sample 1, and (B) sample 2.

Experimental conditions

The experimental setup for the experiments has been described in Section 4, and the standard conditions are summarised in Table 4.1. However the starting pH will be defined by the brine sample.

8.3. Results

From the pH vs charge diagram in Figure 8.2 it can be observed that there are no defined plates that can be identified and related to any specific compound. Both obtained graphs showed the same tendency of a slightly increase over the time, and this is due to the mixture of metals that are present in the solution which precipitate at different conditions. Figure 8.3 shows a picture of the samples (i.e., similar for both samples 1 and 2) after the GDEx treatment. It can be observed that a white turbidity has appeared in the sample which corresponds to the precipitated metals from the solution. Figure 8.4 shows the precipitated solid after drying and grinding.

Figure 8.2. pH evolution during experiments using real geothermal brines from Romania.

Figure 8.3. Sample of real geothermal brines from Romania after GDEx treatment.

Figure 8.4. Solid product obtained using GDEx for the treatment of real geothermal brines from Romania: (A) sample 1, and (B) sample 2.

Analysis of the metal-containing compounds precipitated from each sample has been performed using XRD. The diagrams in Figure 8.5 show the result of this analysis. The main precipitated products identified in every sample are summarised in Table 8.2.

Figure 8.5. XRD analysis of the solid produced during experiments using sample 1 and sample 2 of real geothermal brines from Romania.

Table 8.2. Main compounds identified by XRD in the precipitated product from Sample 1 and Sample 2

Real brine	Main precipitated products
Sample 1	Magnesium hydroxide Strontium manganese oxide Zinc sulfate hydrate
Sample 2	Strontium manganese oxide Calcium iron oxide

In addition, a mass balance of the main compounds present in the samples were performed at two different values of pH. Percentage recovered from the metals in samples 1 and 2 are represented in Figures 8.6 and 8.7 respectively.

Figure 8.6. Percentage (%) of the initial metal recovered in the precipitated product from sample 1 at different pH values.

Figure 8.7. Percentage (%) of the initial metal recovered in the precipitated product from sample 2 at different pH values.

From Figures 8.6 and 8.7 it can be observed that a higher amount of precipitate has been recovered when the GDEx system operates until pH 11, and therefore the energy balance is being developed at this value of pH (Table 8.3). Selectivity on the separation of some metals can be implied.

Table 8.3. Energy balance during experiments using GDEx for the treatment of real geothermal brines (i.e., sample 1 and sample 2) from Romania

Real brine	Energy used (kWh m ⁻³)	Energy used (kWh kg ⁻¹ metal rem.)	Current efficiency (%)
Sample 1	10.26	0.04	44.48
Sample 2	16.86	0.05	52.06

8.4. Conclusions

Obtained results showed that GDEx treatment has demonstrated to be able to precipitate the metals present in two samples of real geothermal brines from Romania. As the matrix contains a different mixture of metals and salts, no defined plates can be observed from the diagram pH vs charge and therefore the selection and separation by precipitation of specific metals cannot be directly done, but the obtained precipitate contains a mixture of various metals. In this specific case, the main metals that have been recovered in the solid product are Mn, Ba, Zn, Sr, As, Li and Al for sample 1 and Sr, Ba, Zn, Ni, As and Rb for sample 2, and the main obtained products in the solid are magnesium hydroxide, strontium manganese oxide and zinc sulfate in case of sample 1, and strontium manganese oxide and calcium iron oxide during the treatment of sample 2 by GDEx. Regarding the energy efficiency of the process, as the metal content in the solution increases, compared with previous experiments with Li/Al simulated brines, the current efficiency of the process is enhanced (45% and 52% for sample 1 and 2 respectively), and the energy used per unit (weight) of metal recovered decreases (0.04-0.05 kWh kg⁻¹ metal removed).

9 Microbial electrochemical anodes

As previously explained, anodes with low cost are needed to make the system economically feasible. Besides, introducing microbial anodes would bring in the opportunity to operate the GDEx system at lower energy input, no input, or even having electricity co-generation. As this has never been tested coupled to GDEx, a feasibility study was here undertaken.

9.1 Principle of metal recovery with GDEx process coupled to bioanodes

In this modified GDEx concept, bioanodes supply energy for hydrogen peroxide production catalyzed by the GDE (carbon based) cathode. H_2O_2 works as intermediate for metal oxides and hydroxides production.

Figure 9.1. Percentage (%) of the initial metal recovered in the precipitated product from sample 2 at different pH values (Adapted from Dominguez-Benetton et al., 2018).

Without the introduction of microbes, the anodic reactions happening in the current system are either the oxygen evolution or the chlorine evolution reaction which take place at theoretical potentials higher than 1.23 V vs. NHE (making in practice the total cell voltage of 3–4 V is achieved). A way to reduce the cell potential (besides the cost of materials by using carbon as the substratum for microbial growth, as opposed to Pt) is selecting an anodic reaction that takes place at a smaller anode potential. Thus, the reaction of choice in this case is the microbial-electrochemical oxidation of acetate:

By this, the electrochemical cell voltage can drop by 5–10 times in practice, compared to the conventional electrolytic cell here operated. Furthermore, by appropriate positioning the anodic and cathodic potentials, the GDEx system could operate not only as an electrolytic cell, but as a galvanic cell, thus providing conditions in which electricity can be cogenerated instead of consumed.

9.2 Biofilm development from two marine sediment sources

Biofilm growth and electroactivity

Two samples from natural salt marshes from France and the Netherlands, respectively were collected. The specific nature of the samples is not relevant for the purpose of demonstration of the concept. These were cultivated in a minimal medium and placed in the vicinity of a polarized carbon material functioning as electrode support. Biofilm growth and stability was observed through the current production over time. Platinum wire used as counter electrode for water reduction, before coupling to the actual GD electrode. The maximum current densities achieved with the bioanodes investigated were in the range of 6–8 A m⁻². These levels of current density are about 10-20 times lower than those required to operate the GDEx process presented in the previous sections at current oxygen reduction rates. Therefore, coupling to the specific bioanodes developed here would imply running the process slower.

Figure 9.2. Current production from two halotolerant bioanodes independently polarized at 0.43 V vs NHE.

9.3 Electrochemical characterization of the MET coupled with a GDE cathode

As the hydrogen peroxide production via the electrochemical oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) in acidic conditions consumes protons (H⁺), the coulombic efficiency (η) is calculated based on the following equation, wherein I is the current, F is Faraday's constant, V is the volume, n is the electrons transferred in the electrochemically-active species.

$$\eta = \frac{\Delta H_{measured}^+}{It (nFV)^{-1}}$$

Figure 9.3 presents the polarization curve in electrolysis mode (external current source), and the coulombic efficiency based on the proton transport. On the basis of this curve, the bioanode and cathode potential behavior at different current densities was evaluated and is presented in Figure 9.4, proving that coupling the bioanode to the GDEx cathode is feasible in electrolysis mode, mainlining the possibility to conduct the oxygen reduction reaction to hydrogen peroxide.

Figure 9.3. Coulombic efficiency and power generated over the Dutch cell. Current densities are normalized to the cathode projected area. $pH_{catholyte}$: 3, $pH_{anolyte}$: 7.5, stabilization time: 10 min.

Figure 9.4. Bioanode and cathode potential behavior at different current densities. Current densities are normalized to the cathode projected area. $pH_{catholyte}$: 3, $pH_{anolyte}$: 7.5, stabilization time: 10 min.

Figure 9.5 presents the power curve in microbial fuel cell mode (external resistance), and the current density generated. On the basis of this curve, the bioanode and cathode potential behavior at different current densities was evaluated and is presented in Figure 9.6, proving that coupling the bioanode to the GDEx cathode is feasible in galvanic mode, bringing the possibility to cogenerate electricity while achieving metal recovery with the GDEx process.

Figure 9.5. Current and power density at different resistances over the Dutch cell. Current densities are normalized to the cathode projected area. $pH_{catholyte}$: 3, $pH_{anolyte}$: 7.5, stabilization time: 15 min.

Figure 9.6. Bioanode and cathode potential behavior at different resistance. $pH_{catholyte}$: 3, $pH_{anolyte}$: 7.5, stabilization time: 15 min.

9.4. Conclusions

Given the performance shown for the bioanodes coupled to the GD electrode in GDEx conditions, it is feasible to couple these components to achieve metal precipitation under the previously described conditions, at lower rates. Higher rates could be eventually achieved with better performing bioanodes.

10 References

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ANNEXES

ANNEX 1. Literature survey on geothermal brines characterization

Anions

Place Place description	California US Imperial Valley	New Zealand Wairakei	Philippines Palinpinon	California US Salton Sea Plant	Papua New Guinea Ladolam	New Zealand Wairakei	France-Germany Upper Rhine Graben	Iceland Reykjanes	Iceland Reykjanes	Iceland Reykjanes	UK Carmmenellis Region	Romania Sample 1	Romania Sample 2	Belgium Mol
Depth (m)			3.12-8.23	5.2-5.6	360-1500	950	1547-5000	1500	1500	1350	690	7.9	8.2	3280
pH					7.12-8.69		5.06-6.92				5.38-6.79			
Temperature (°C)	105	60-80	320-330		>275		35-91.7	296	285	284	34.3-45.3			125
Conductivity (mS cm ⁻¹)							23-158							
Characterization (ppm)														
Total solids (g L ⁻¹)				190-294							9226-14099			
TDS							15.6-201							
TIC							11.4-127							
TOC							0.7-35.2							
SiO ₂		530	155-1120	200-506	540-662		35.8-201	618	7049	671				102.5
H ₂ SiO ₃														133.2
H ₂ S			0.75-62.6											
NH ₃			0.92-36	45-440			1.65-47.4 (NH ₄)							264 (NH ₄)
ANIONS														
As		6.4		0.2-7	1.5-18.0	51	0.021-11.6	0.113	0.117	0.154				
Br					13-39	2400	2.5-726	65	72	61		<0.5	<0.5	134
Cl			1062-7205		7000-19860		6375-120500	19283	18806	19410	5800-8750	<5	<5	100200
F							0.85-31.8					1	0.52	<0.88
I (ppb)								1118	369	460				
S								40	27	38				
Se				6				0.01	0.002	0.004				
Te (ppb)					<1-4	0.4		19	31	63				
NO ₃							<0.5					<2.5	<2.5	
SO ₄			10.6-954		7511-31380		126-2730				107-240	1100	60	380
PO ₄							<0.1-3.1							
CO ₃			19.5-144		702-2765									1129
Reference	CEC, 2014	Mroczek et al, 2015	Rae et al 2011	Maimoni 1982	Simmons and Brown 2006	Sanjuan et al 2016		Hardardottir et al 2009, 2010, 2011	Smedley et al 1989					Current study

Cations

Place Place description	California US Imperial Valley	New Zealand Wairakei	Philippines Palinpinon	California US Salton Sea Plant	Papua New Guinea Ladolam	New Zealand Wairakei	France-Germany Upper Rhine Graben	Iceland Reykjanes	Iceland Reykjanes	Iceland Reykjanes	UK Carmmenellis Region	Romania Sample 1	Romania Sample 2	Belgium Mol
Depth (m)					360-1500	950	1547-5000	1500	1500	1350	690			3280
Characterization (ppm)														
Ag				0.5	<0.001-0.005	0.0006	<0.0001-0.0015	0.036	0.028	0.107				
Al		1.5					0.005-0.094	2.8	0.4	1.4	<0.4-6			
Au				0.1	0.001-0.016	<0.0001		0.006	0.001	0.001				
As														
B		28	29.2-83.4	10-300	41-151	0.3	3.9-45.9	8	8	7.7	5.9-12.2			
Ba				290			0.05-17.6	10.1	10.8	10.8	0.508-0.872			16.5
Be (ppb)							1.52-22.7							
Bi				5										
Ca		18	0.2-213.9		9.1-30		719-11700	1940	17459	1843	1070-1920	303	50.9	9130
Cd (ppb)							<0.1-55.9	136	56	181	<120			
Co				0.3			<0.0005-0.005				<0.08			
Cr (ppb)							<1-1.04	24	11	141	<160			
Cs			0.92-3.56				0.204-19.3				2.60-6.56			
Cu				0.8-3	0.01-4.45	0.022	<0.001-0.372	17.2	13.7	14	<0.08			
Fe		0.8		422-1300	0.07		0.14-78.0	24.9	8.9	141	1.82-5.22			806
Ge (ppb)							10.3-70.4							
Hg (ppb)					0.7-1	0.52		0.6	0.5	0.4				
K	29000	165	151-858	8500-14300	1440-5057	<0.1	155-4030	1542	1529	1675	63.2-138	12.8	5.79	2870
Li	250	11	5.6-18.10	117-245			4.5-210	6.4	6.5	6.8	54.4-97.2			
Mg		0.1	0.06-21.10	68-75	0.1		76.0-1930	9.9	2	4.3	33.2-110	85.6		560
Mn	1500			565-1260	0.12-4.90	0.038	0.015-26.1	3	2	2.8	2.58-6.68			13.6
Mo				4	0.010-0.43	0.006		0.015	0.013	0.034				
Na		111	1380-3977		7300-26240	0.5	4400-64000	9378	9299	9493	1890-3210			49600
Ni (ppb)							1.06-67.3	221	146	54	<200-400			
Pb				70-90	<0.001-0.040	0.015	<0.0005-3.39	0.29	0.118	0.293				
Pt				0.06										
Rb			1.49-4.84	25-56			0.65-30.2				1.06-3.26			
Sb				4	<0.001-0.004	0.019	0.0574-0.267	0.026	0.019	0.047				
Si											14.4-19.6			47.9
Sn				23	0.011-0.84	0.0077		0.001	0.001	0.007				
Sr				366-600			12.1-498	9.1	9.6	9.5	17.6-31.6			400
Th (ppb)							0.00019-0.00092							
Tl (ppb)					2-69	<0.1		12	11	13				
V (ppb)					7-950	<0.01		13	5	21				
W (ppb)								6	6	21				
Zn	500			226-500	0.185-0.3	0.125	0.018-15.2	26.7	5.4	13				
RARE EARTH ELEMENTS														
Nd (ppb)							0.13-0.538							
U (ppb)							0.007-0.033							
Reference	CEC, 2014	Mroczek et al, 2015	Rae et al 2011	Maimoni 1982	Simmons and Brown 2006		Sanjuan et al 2016	Hardardottir et al 2009, 2010, 2011			Smedley et al 1989		Current study	

ANNEX 2. Chemical characterization from real geothermal brines from Romania

Parameter	Units	Sample 1		Sample 2	
		Total	Filtered	Total	Filtered
pH		7.9		8.2	
Sulfate	mg L ⁻¹	1100	1100	60	59
NO ₂ -N	mg N L ⁻¹	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1	<0,1
NO ₃ -N	mg N L ⁻¹	<2,5	<2,5	<2,5	<2,5
Bromide	mg L ⁻¹	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5	<0,5
Fluoride	mg L ⁻¹	1	1	0.52	0.51
Chloride	mg L ⁻¹	<5	<5	<5	<5
Ca	µg L ⁻¹	303000	303000	50900	50800
K	µg L ⁻¹	12800	12800	5790	5760
Mg	µg L ⁻¹	85600	85600	20500	20500
Na	µg L ⁻¹	29700	29700	12100	12100
Sr	µg L ⁻¹	12400	12400	727	726
Metals					
Sr	µg L ⁻¹	12040	12040	760	650
Fe	µg L ⁻¹	2300	<10	33	<10
Li	µg L ⁻¹	129	129	33	33
Al	µg L ⁻¹	44	<10	<10	<10
Mn	µg L ⁻¹	40	39	<1	<1
Ba	µg L ⁻¹	32	32	81	81
Rb	µg L ⁻¹	16	16	14	14
As	µg L ⁻¹	9	3.8	5.7	5.7
Cs	µg L ⁻¹	2.5	2.5	2.3	2.3
Zn	µg L ⁻¹	1.5	1.5	62	62
Mo	µg L ⁻¹	1.3	1.3	1	1
Cu	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	8	8
Os	µg L ⁻¹	<10	<10	<10	<10
Be	µg L ⁻¹	<10	<10	<10	<10
Ni	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	13	12
Pb	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	1.3	<1
V	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Cr	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Co	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Ga	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Pd	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Cd	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Sn	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Sb	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Te)	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Au	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Tl	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1

U	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Ti	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Se	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Ru	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Ag	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Hf	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Ir	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Pt	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Rare earth elements (REE)					
Ce	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Dy	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Er	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Eu	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Gd	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Eu	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
La	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Lu	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Nd	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Pr	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Sc	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Sm	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Tb	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Th	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Tm	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
U	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Y	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Yb	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Bi	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Nb	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Re	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Ta	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
W	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1
Zr	µg L ⁻¹	<1	<1	<1	<1